

2nd BONBID-HIE Challenge for HIE Outcome Prediction and Lesion Segmentation: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

2nd BONBID-HIE Challenge for HIE Outcome Prediction and Lesion Segmentation

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

BONBID-HIE

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Hypoxic-Ischemic Encephalopathy (HIE) is a severe neonatal brain injury that affects around 0.5% of newborns globally [1,2]. Despite advancements Therapeutic Hypothermia (TH), introduced in 2005, the prognosis for many infants remains challenging, with a considerable percentage (35%-50%) suffering adverse outcomes [3-5]. A key issue is the limited ability to identify high-risk infants early and accurately assess therapeutic outcomes before age two [6]. This highlights an urgent need for precise and reliable biomarkers for early and accurate prognosis. Last year (2023), we held the first HIE brain MRI challenge. The task was to segment the HIE-related lesions in infant brain MRI. Totally 120 research groups downloaded our data and 14 algorithms were submitted. Built on last year's success, we propose a second-year challenge in MICCAI 2024, with two aims: (1) lesion segmentation in infant brain MRIs; and (2) 2-year neurologic outcome prediction using infant brain MRIs. The first aim is an extension of the first challenge in 2023, in that more brain MRIs without explicit lesion annotation will be provided to allow unsupervised algorithm development. The second aim is new and carries the ultimate clinical significance.

Our data is the first public data for these tasks on HIE patients. This data was derived from clinical workflows over the past 20 years and a 3-4 year process of retrospective collection, curation, and annotation. Our laboratory, supported by grants R03, R61, and R21, has spent a decade meticulously organizing data, resulting in a dataset of nearly 300 samples.

Technically, segmenting HIE MRI data is notably more complex than other tasks, such as segmenting brain tumors with larger, focal lesions (Dice: 0.8 and above). So, this HIE challenge represents AI tasks on small diffuse lesions, different from many other segmentation and recognition tasks on big focal target regions.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.challenge_

Neonatal Brain Injury, Hypoxic Ischemic Encephalopathy, Lesion Segmentation, Small Diffuse Lesion, Outcome Prediction

Year

The challenge will take place in 2024

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

2nd Workshop on BONBID-HIE Lesion Segmentation and Outcome Prediction

<https://hiechallenge.github.io/>

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

Last year, we have over 120 registered participants worldwide for one task of single site HIE lesion segmentation [7].

This year, we have two tracks from multi-site data for lesion segmentation and outcome prediction. Therefore, we believe this challenge will attract more participants than last year who are working on pediatric brain injuries and who may want to migrate their adult-based brain injury detection and classification algorithms to pediatric populations. For example, algorithm developers working on segmenting brain tumors, multiple sclerosis, stroke lesions, white matter hyperintensity lesions, epilepsy, and other brain abnormalities may want to test their algorithms in the neonatal brain injury context, for small diffuse lesions. Besides, algorithms developers who are working on brain MRI disease classification may also be interested in testing their algorithms in this brain injury outcome task.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

We plan to publish at least one paper in the top journal of medical image analysis to summarize the challenge results and discuss the future research direction. Members in the top or all teams will be co-authors, depending on the number of participating teams. In the paper, we will publish a substantial summary of the challenge results.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

To achieve a fair comparison and computing environment, we will utilize the following measures: The official platform for medical challenges : <https://bonbid-hie2023.grand-challenge.org/> will be used as the on-site evaluation platform to publish evaluation metrics, update the leaderboard, and rank methods. All results of algorithms are run on the same evaluation platform based on the same evaluation codes to guarantee the fairness of the comparison. All algorithms will be required to upload their dockers to run on the held-out test datasets for final evaluation.

TASK 1: HIE Lesion Segmentation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Accurate detection of HIE lesions is crucial, as it can provide valuable insights for clinical objectives such as predicting outcomes in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) or assessing neurocognitive developments by age 2. The HIE lesion segmentation challenge will feature the largest publicly available multi-site MRI dataset for this critical brain abnormality. In contrast, many leading HIE segmentation studies often rely on proprietary data with only a few dozen samples. HIE-related brain abnormalities in brain MRI are often diffuse (i.e., multi-focal), and small (over half the patients having lesions occupying <1% of the brain volume). Segmenting HIE in MRI data is distinctively more challenging compared to other segmentation tasks like large, focal brain tumors. The design of methods for HIE lesion segmentation requires particular attention due to the highly unbalanced nature of the data and significant variations in lesion size and location. This dataset comprises data collected and curated retrospectively over 20 years from clinical workflows, with an extensive annotation process spanning 3-4 years. The project is funded by an NIH R03 grant (2021-2023), making it a significantly large sample for this disease, particularly given the rarity of annotations from skilled pediatric/neonatal neuroradiologists. Last year (2023), we hosted the first HIE brain MRI challenge, focusing on the segmentation of HIE-related lesions in infant brain MRI. A total of 120 research groups accessed our data, leading to 14 algorithm submissions. Building on this success, we are organizing a second challenge at MICCAI 2024. This year's task expands upon the previous challenge, offering additional brain MRIs without explicit lesion annotations to facilitate the development of unsupervised and semi-supervised algorithms. We anticipate that the HIE lesion segmentation challenge with MRI will stimulate new research in learning MRI segmentation from limited data and alleviate the diagnostic burden for medical professionals dealing with HIE.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Neonatal Brain Injury, Hypoxic Ischemic Encephalopathy, Lesion Segmentation, Small Diffuse Lesion

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Rina Bao, PhD, Research Fellow,
Boston Children's Hospital, Harvard Medical School

P. Ellen Grant, MD
Professor of Radiology and Pediatrics at Harvard Medical School

Yangming Ou, PhD, Associate Professor,
Department of Radiology at Harvard Medical School

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

rina.bao@childrens.harvard.edu

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2024

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge <https://bonbid-hie2023.grand-challenge.org/>

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://bonbid-hie2023.grand-challenge.org/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Private data is allowed. Publicly available data is allowed.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

Top team awards will be awarded to the teams that obtain top scores in the challenge leaderboard with submitted docker file and complete technical paper submissions reviewed by the organizing committee.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All submitted methods will be announced publicly.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

The challenge organizers will publish at least one journal paper with high impact about the challenge. The top teams will be invited as co-authors. Participating teams may publish their own results separately after the challenge. No embargo time is defined.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker container on grand challenge platform

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Our challenge incorporates a three-stage process designed to ensure thorough testing and validation of algorithms and docker containers.

(1) Training Stage: We will release all ground truth masks for the training data, and all evaluation codes will be available on our website. This allows participants to evaluate the performance of their models on the training data during this phase and to perform cross-validation.

(2) Evaluation Stage: Participating teams can submit docker files of their algorithms for a sanity check with our validation set on the grand challenge website of our challenge.

(3) Test Stage: Participating teams can submit docker files of their algorithms for hidden test cases through the grand challenge website. The final ranking will be based on performance in this stage. Each team will have three opportunities for submission, but only the last run will be officially counted when computing the challenge results.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period

- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Release date of training data: 04/30/2024

Registration date: 04/30/2024

Release date of test cases: 08/01/2024

Submission date: development stage: 07/01/2024-07/31/2024

test stage: 08/01/2024-08/31/2024

Release date of results: 10/01/2024

Associated workshop date: 10/10/2024

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The release of the MRI data and expert annotations of lesions have been approved by IRB-P00025916 at Boston Children's Hospital and IRB-2021P003584 at Massachusetts General Hospital.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Evaluation codes <https://github.com/baorina/BONBID-HIE-MICCAI2023/tree/main>

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

All participating teams are required to submit a docker file of their algorithms. Top teams are required to make their codes publicly available on grand challenge.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

NIH grant R03 HD104891, test cases are hidden during the challenge, but will be released after the challenge.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Prognosis, Diagnosis, Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration

- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Team-born infants with clinically-confirmed hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy who have undergone brain MRI (structural and diffusion sequences) in 0-14 days of postnatal life.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Team-born infants with clinically-confirmed hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy at Massachusetts General Hospital and Boston Children's Hospital who had undergone brain MRI (structural and diffusion sequences) in 0-14 days of postnatal life during 2001-2018.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

MRIs were acquired on either GE 1.5T Signa scanner (N=52, scanned during 2001-2012) or Siemens 3T Trio scanner (N=81, scanned during 2012-2018). Diffusion tensor imaging has the protocol as follows: TR=7500-9500 ms, TE=80-115 ms, b=1000 s/mm², voxel size=2 × 2 × 2 mm³ and 30 diffusion directions (Siemens scanner) or 1.5 × 1.5 × (4.0-6.0) mm³ and 6 diffusion directions (GE scanner). ADC maps were generated by the scanner.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

[0%, 1%) of the brain being injured 55.64% (N=74)

[1, 5%) of the brain was injured 19.55% (N=26)

[5, 10%) of the brain was injured 5.26% (N=7)

[10, 20%) of the brain was injured 4.51% (N=6)

[20, 50%) of the brain was injured 8.27% (N=11)

[50, 100] % of the brain was injured 6.77% (N=9)

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Sex: 53% M / 47% F

Age at scan: median 4 days (0-14 postnatal)

Gestational age at birth: 39.2 +/- 1.9 weeks

Birth weight: 3.3 +/- 0.6 kg

Maternal age at birth: 29.4 +/- 6.6 years

Head circumferences: 34.3 +/- 1.6 cm

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Target cohort: patients who have confirmed with hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy and who have undergone structural and diffusion brain MRI.

Challenge cohort: Patients who have been clinically cared at the Massachusetts General Hospital and Boston Children's Hospital during 2001-2018 with structural and diffusion brain MRI.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Abnormality (brain injury) in the brain MRI.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Find lesion segmentation algorithm for MRI images with high Dice in brain MRIs of neonates with hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

MRIs were acquired on either GE 1.5T Signa scanner (scanned during 2001-2012) or Siemens 3T Trio scanner (scanned during 2012-2018).

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

ADC Maps: MRIs were acquired on either GE 1.5T Signa scanner (N=52, scanned during 2001-2012) or Siemens 3T Trio scanner (N=81, scanned during 2012-2018). Diffusion tensor imaging has the protocol as follows:

TR=7500/9500 ms, TE=80/115 ms, b=1000s/mm², voxel size=2 × 2 × 2 mm³ and 30 diffusion directions (Siemens scanner) or 1.5 × 1.5 × (4.0/6.0) mm³ and 6 diffusion directions (GE scanner). ADC maps were generated by the scanner.

Z-score Maps: Z-score maps are maps that quantify location-specific deviation from normal. First, an average atlas space is generated through unbiased group-wise image registration. Then, a deformation D is computed, which mapped every voxel x in the patient's ADC map to its anatomically-corresponding location D(x) in the atlas space. The normal range of ADC variation was defined by the mean and standard deviation denoted as $\mu(x)$ and $\sigma(x)$ for this voxel. Finally, the patient's ADC value I_x at voxel x was converted to a Z value: $Z_x = (I_x - \mu(x)) / \sigma(x)$. Therefore,

the Z-score value at voxel location x quantified how many standard deviations away this patient's ADC value I_x was from the mean normal ADC value at this anatomical location. ADC maps from 24 term-born healthy neonates acquired at the same hospital using Siemens 3T Trio scanner (median 4 days after birth) went through distortion/motion correction (FSL tool) and skull-stripping.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Massachusetts General Hospital, Boston Children's Hospital

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

NA

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in the HIE study. This information includes the ADC maps and Zmaps.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Training: 89 cases (annotated) + 72 cases (unannotated)

Test: 44 cases

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

Testing cases include 22, 12, and 10 patients whose lesion volume occupied <1%, 1-5%, and >5% of the whole brain volume. In each category, half of the patients were scanned on the GE 1.5T and remaining half on Siemens 3T. This is to quantify the algorithm's accuracy with regard to lesion volume and scanner.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

NA

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

We have 1 primary annotator and 3 more senior as-needed annotators. The manual annotation of lesions was done by the primary annotator. And in case there is uncertainty (-1/5 of the patients), the three as-needed senior annotators discussed and formed a consensus. Eventually, there was 1 annotated binary lesion image for each patient.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Annotation was done in MRICroN, with further edits from FSL and AFNI tools.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The primary annotator has medical training and has reference from the radiology report. The three as needed senior annotators are experts with over 5, 5, and 20 years of pediatric neuroradiology experience.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Consensus of annotated masks by the STAPLE algorithm.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N4 bias correction, skull stripping, brain extraction.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Uncertainties in the small diffuse abnormalities may cause errors. However, we don't have a quantitative measurement of such intra-/inter-expert errors in the literature or in our data.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

As the diffusion MRI was 2x2x2 mm in voxel size, so the resolution of the lesion annotation is bounded by this voxel resolution.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

The submission will be evaluated based on the Dice (Dice coefficient [8]) +-std, MASD+-std (Mean Average Surface Distance [9]) and NSD+-std (Normalized Surface Distance [10,11]) for different percentage lesions (<1%, 1%-5%, > 5%).

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

We use Dice+-std, MASD+-std and NSD+-std for evaluation. Dice is widely used in medical segmentation challenges and tasks. However, it is not ideal for evaluating small diffuse lesions. Boundary-based metrics maybe appropriate. Therefore, we add MASD and NSD for evaluation.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

Ranking schemes are used in many similar medical segmentation challenges, such as ISLES.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If some cases are missing from the results, the Dice will be set to zero. The MASD and NSD will be set as the prediction with all voxels predicted as background. We will also return the information of missing cases to the participating team.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

- (1) Compute the Dice+-std, MASD+-std, and NSD+-std values for each case.
- (2) Establish each team's rank for Dice+-std, MASD+-std and NSD+-std separately for each case.
- (3) Compute the mean rank over all three evaluation measures and std /case to obtain the team's rank for the case.
- (4) Compute the mean overall case-specific ranks to obtain the team's final rank.

We will maintain two separate leaderboards. The first leaderboard will exclusively use the provided training dataset to rank the performance of the submitted methods. The second leaderboard will be used for ranking

methods that utilize pretrained models or other publicly available datasets.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Data that is missing will be assigned a value of 0 for Dice, sensitivity, and specificity metrics. The algorithms will be ranked based on overall accuracy, as well as accuracy across various scanners and lesion volumes. A t-test will be utilized to determine if there is a statistically significant difference between any two algorithms. Additionally, we will aggregate the results from all participating teams using the STAPLE algorithm to form a consensus. We aim to test the hypothesis that this consensus result is more accurate and stable than the results from individual participating teams, using a t-test and evaluating the p-value.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

Dice, MASD, and NSD metrics are represented as floating-point numbers, and to determine whether there is a statistically significant difference between two algorithms, we will employ the T-test for comparison. Consensus among all participating algorithms will be done by the STAPLE algorithm, which has been commonly used in medical image segmentation tasks to form consensus from multiple segmentation results.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

A review paper of submitted methods will be published based on the analysis of the submitted algorithms about inter-algorithm variability, common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or ranking variability. We will also compare this year's segmentation methods and performances with those from last year's challenge.

TASK 2: HIE 2-year Neurocognitive Outcome Prediction

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Hypoxic Ischemic Encephalopathy (HIE) is a severe neonatal brain injury that affects around 0.5% of newborns globally [1,2]. Despite advancements in Therapeutic Hypothermia (TH), introduced in 2005, the prognosis for many infants remains challenging, with a considerable percentage (35%-50%) suffering adverse outcomes [3-5]. A key issue is the limited ability to identify high-risk infants early and accurately assess therapeutic outcomes before age two [6]. This highlights an urgent need for precise and reliable biomarkers for early and accurate prognosis. Predicting neurocognitive outcome is a key issue for establishing reliable and accurate HIE biomarkers. Last year (2023), we held the first HIE brain MRI challenge. The task was to segment the HIE-related lesions in infant brain MRI. In total, 120 research groups downloaded our data, and 14 algorithms were submitted. Building on last year's success, we propose a new aim this year: 2-year neurocognitive outcome prediction using infant brain MRIs, which is new and carries the ultimate clinical significance.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Neonatal Brain Injury, Hypoxic Ischemic Encephalopathy, Neurocognitive Outcome Prediction

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Rina Bao, PhD, Research Fellow,

Boston Children's Hospital, Harvard Medical School

P. Ellen Grant, MD

Professor of Radiology and Pediatrics at Harvard Medical School

Yangming Ou, PhD, Associate Professor,

Department of Radiology at Harvard Medical School

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

rina.bao@childrens.harvard.edu

Life cycle type

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Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2024

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge <https://bonbid-hie2023.grand-challenge.org/>

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://bonbid-hie2023.grand-challenge.org/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Private data is allowed. Publicly available data is allowed.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

Top team awards will be awarded to the teams that obtain top scores in the challenge leaderboard with submitted docker file and complete technical paper submissions reviewed by the organizing committee.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All submitted methods will be announced publicly.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)

- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

The challenge organizers will publish at least one journal paper with high impact about the challenge. The top teams will be invited as co-authors. Participating teams may publish their own results separately after the challenge. No embargo time is defined.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker container on grand challenge platform

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Our challenge incorporates a three-stage process designed to ensure thorough testing and validation of algorithms and docker containers.

(1) Training Stage: We will release all ground truth masks for the training data, and all evaluation codes will be available on our website. This allows participants to evaluate the performance of their models on the training data during this phase and to perform cross-validation.

(2) Evaluation Stage: Participating teams can submit docker files of their algorithms for a sanity check with our validation set on the grand challenge website of our challenge.

(3) Test Stage: Participating teams can submit docker files of their algorithms for hidden test cases through the grand challenge website. The final ranking will be based on performance in this stage. Each team will have three opportunities for submission, but only the last run will be officially counted when computing the challenge results.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Release date of training data: 04/30/2024

Registration date: 04/30/2024

Release date of test cases: 08/01/2024

Submission date: development stage: 07/01/2024-07/31/2024

test stage: 08/01/2024-08/31/2024

Release date of results: 10/01/2024

Associated workshop date: 10/10/2024

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The release of the MRI data and expert annotations of lesions have been approved by IRB-P00025916 at Boston Children's Hospital and IRB-2021P003584 at Massachusetts General Hospital.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Evaluation codes <https://github.com/baorina/BONBID-HIE-MICCAI2023/tree/main>

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

All participating teams are required to submit a docker file of their algorithms. Top teams are required to make their codes publicly available on grand challenge.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

NIH grant R03 HD104891, test cases are hidden during the challenge, but will be released after the challenge.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Prognosis, Diagnosis, Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics

defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

Team-born infants with clinically-confirmed hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy who have undergone brain MRI (structural and diffusion sequences) in 0-14 days of postnatal life.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Team-born infants with clinically-confirmed hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy at Massachusetts General Hospital and Boston Children's Hospital who had undergone brain MRI (structural and diffusion sequences) in 0-14 days of postnatal life during 2001-2018.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

MRIs were acquired on either GE 1.5T Signa scanner (N=52, scanned during 2001-2012) or Siemens 3T Trio scanner (N=81, scanned during 2012-2018). Diffusion tensor imaging has the protocol as follows: TR=7500-9500 ms, TE=80-115 ms, b=1000 s/mm², voxel size=2 × 2 × 2 mm³ and 30 diffusion directions (Siemens scanner) or 1.5 × 1.5 × (4.0-6.0) mm³ and 6 diffusion directions (GE scanner). ADC maps were generated by the scanner.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

[0%, 1%) of the brain being injured 55.64% (N=74)

[1, 5%) of the brain was injured 19.55% (N=26)

[5, 10%) of the brain was injured 5.26% (N=7)

[10, 20%) of the brain was injured 4.51% (N=6)

[20, 50%) of the brain was injured 8.27% (N=11)

[50, 100] % of the brain was injured 6.77% (N=9)

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Sex: 58% M / 42% F

Age at scan: median 4 days (0-14 postnatal)

Gestational age at birth: 39.1 +/- 1.9 weeks

Birth weight: 3.3 +/- 0.6 kg

Maternal age at birth: 30.4 +/- 6.0 years

Head circumferences: 34.3 +/- 1.6 cm

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Target cohort: patients who have confirmed with hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy and who have undergone structural and diffusion brain MRI.

Challenge cohort: Patients who have been clinically cared at the Massachusetts General Hospital and Boston Children's Hospital during 2001-2018 with structural and diffusion brain MRI.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

2-year neurocognitive outcome

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy of predicting normal/adverse outcome of neonates with hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy (binary classification)

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

MRIs were acquired on either GE 1.5T Signa scanner (scanned during 2001-2012) or Siemens 3T Trio scanner (scanned during 2012-2018).

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

ADC Maps: MRIs were acquired on either GE 1.5T Signa scanner (N=52, scanned during 2001-2012) or Siemens 3T Trio scanner (N=81, scanned during 2012-2018). Diffusion tensor imaging has the protocol as follows: TR=7500/9500 ms, TE=80/115 ms, b=1000s/mm², voxel size=2 × 2 × 2 mm³ and 30 diffusion directions (Siemens scanner) or 1.5 × 1.5 × (4.0/6.0) mm³ and 6 diffusion directions (GE scanner). ADC maps were generated by the scanner.

Z-score Maps: Z-score maps are maps that quantify location-specific deviation from normal. First, an average atlas space is generated through unbiased group-wise image registration. Then, a deformation D is computed, which mapped every voxel x in the patient's ADC map to its anatomically-corresponding location D(x) in the atlas space. The normal range of ADC variation was defined by the mean and standard deviation denoted as $\mu(x)$ and $\sigma(x)$ for this voxel. Finally, the patient's ADC value Ix at voxel x was converted to a Z value: $Z_x = (I_x - \mu(x)) / \sigma(x)$. Therefore, the Z-score value at voxel location x quantified how many standard deviations away this patient's ADC value Ix

was from the mean normal ADC value at this anatomical location. ADC maps from 24 term-born healthy neonates acquired at the same hospital using Siemens 3T Trio scanner (median 4 days after birth) went through distortion/motion correction (FSL tool) and skull-stripping.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Massachusetts General Hospital, Boston Children's Hospital

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

NA

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in the HIE study. This information includes the ADC maps and Zmaps.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

We have total 156 cases, 72/156 are from Boston Children's Hospital, and 84/156 are from Mass General Hospital.

Training: 109 cases

Testing: 47 cases

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

Based on 70% training, 30% testing.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

NA

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

We have 1 primary annotator and 3 more senior as-needed annotators.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Annotation was done in MRICroN, with information from clinical reports.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The primary annotator has medical training and has reference from the radiology report. The three as needed senior annotators are experts with over 5, 5, and 20 years of pediatric neuroradiology experience.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Consensus among all annotators.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N4 bias correction, skull stripping, brain extraction.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

NA

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

NA

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Neurocognitive outcome prediction is a binary classification problem (normal outcome vs adverse outcome). Therefore, accuracy, Area under curve, Specificity, Sensitivity will be used to evaluate algorithms.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Neurocognitive outcome prediction is a binary classification problem (normal outcome vs adverse outcome). Therefore, accuracy, Area under curve, Specificity, Sensitivity will be used to evaluate algorithms since these metrics are widely used to evaluate medical image classification performance.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

Ranking schemes are used in many similar medical image classification.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If the result for a case is missing, the accuracy will be designated as 0.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The ultimate rankings are determined by overall accuracy, Area Under the Curve (AUC), specificity, and sensitivity

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

We will rank the algorithms for overall accuracy, and accuracy in different sites. T-test will be used to decide with two algorithms are statistically different.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

NA

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

A review paper of submitted methods will be published based on the analysis of the submitted algorithms about inter-algorithm variability on different sites, common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or ranking variability.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

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8. L. R. Dice, Measures of the amount of ecologic association between species, *Ecology*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 297-302, 1945.
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Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A